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Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs (AIJACLA) is an annual international double-blind peer-reviewed journal in the field of law. The journal deals with contemporary affairs primarily within the discipline of law but also encourages interdisciplinary research works from any discipline provided the relation of the subject-matter with the legal institutions, legal instruments, or any other legal matters shall be established and highlighted to meet the eligibility criteria of the journal.

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4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

SI No.	Title of Papers and Names and Designations of Authors	Page No.
SECTION A: RESEARCH PAPERS		
1	Affirmative Principle: Making, Breaking and Shaking (MBS) Approach of Judiciary <i>-Dr Rangswami D, Assistant Professor of Law, Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, Karnataka</i>	1 - 17
2	Clinical and Continuing Legal Education- Interface for Confidence Building Between Law Students and Legal Professionals in Contemporary India <i>- Dr. Md. Sultan Haidar Alam, Principal, NERIM Law College</i>	18 - 29
3	A Critical Appraisal of the Legal Service Authorities Act with Special Reference to Lok Adalat <i>- Dr. Dhiraj Bhusan Sarmah, Former Faculty of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University & Dr. Plabita Saikia, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	30 - 49
4	Establishment of DNA Data Bank in India: A Legal Analysis <i>- Dr. Ranjit Sil, Assistant Professor, Department Of Law, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong</i>	50 - 64
5	Ecocentric Approaches of the Restorative Justice Theory Vis-à-vis the Legal Issues of Civil and Criminal Liability of the Baghjan Blowout Case in Assam <i>- Dr. Matiur Rahman, Assistant Professor of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University</i>	65 - 76
6	A Comparative Study on Secondary Patenting on Pharmaceutical: Striking A Balance Between Competition Law and IPR <i>- Dr. Kakumani Katakya, Faculty of Law Gauhati University</i>	77 - 90
7	Community and Environmental Protection- - In Search of the Lost Spring of Happiness of the North-Eastern Region <i>- Dr. Sujata Bhattacharyya, Principal, Nowgong Law College</i>	91 - 106
8	National Emergency: A Comparative Analysis of Emergency Laws in India USA and Germany <i>- Abhishek Kumar Khaund, Advocate. Gauhati High Court</i>	107 - 124
9	Legal Frameworks Relating to Use of Pesticides on Horticultural Activities Vis-à-vis Climate Change <i>- Bonani Deori, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Mritunjoy Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	125 -145
20	The Arms Act, 1959: A Legal Analysis and Comparative Study with USA <i>- Bikash Sen Deka, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	146 -168
11	Comparative Study on Intergovernmental Tax Immunities under the Federal Constitutions of Australia, Canada, India and USA <i>- Bandita Das, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	169 - 177
12	Unlawful Activities and Prevention Act: Balancing National Security with Citizen's Rights <i>- Girisha Sinha, Research Assistant under Advocate Ritesh Kumar Patna High Court</i>	178 - 191
13	An Analysis of the Legal Framework of the Co-operative Banks in India	192 - 215

	- Bidikha Gogoi, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
14	Parole- The Reformative Instrument of Punishment in Prisonization	216 -228
	- Nayana Medhi, Former Faculty of Law, Indraprastha University	
15	Assam Police and Its Organizational Structure	229 - 271
	- Dr. Anup Kr. Ray, Principal, Goalpara Law College	
SECTION B: ARTICLES		
16	Anti-Defection Law: A Conflict Between the Right to Dissent and the Integrity of the Political Party	273 - 281
	- Apurva Mehta, B.A. LL.B. (Criminal Law Hons.), 5th Year, National University of Study and Research in Law, Ranchi	
17	Contempt of Court: An Urgent Requisite to Re-Explore	282 - 287
	- Paras Gupta, B.A.LL.B.(Hons.), Institute of Law, Kurukshetra University	
18	Lack of Uniform Code of Conduct to Address the Judges in India	288 - 294
	- Saloni Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology & Riya Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology	
19	Rejuvenating the Right to Equality and Life under the Paradigm of Transformative Constitution	295 - 301
	- Dr. Daisy Changmai, Faculty of Law, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam, Former Principal of Dibrugarh Hanumanbux Surojmal Kanoi Law College	
20	Genital Mutilation- An Appeal for Legislative Response in India to Outlaw the Menace	302 - 311
	- Dr. Karavi Barman, Assistant Professor, N.E.F Law College, Guwahati	
21	Surrogacy in India: A Legal Perspective	312 - 319
	- Dr. Shrutimala Goswami, Assistant Professor, NERIM Law College & Arunav Barua., Research Scholar, Assam Don Bosco University	
22	Merger and Amalgamation of Companies in India: AN Analysis of Its Impact on Various Stakeholders	320 - 330
	- Purbaja Sarmah, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
23	Human Rights Crisis amongst IDPs in Assam: Issues and Challenges	331 - 337
	- Dr. Gautami Dutta, Principal, Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Dibrugarh	
24	Protective Discrimination under the Constitution of India	338 -345
	- Pallabi Nath, LL.M 1 st Semester, Tezpur University	
25	Mob Lynching as a New Offence Emerging in India: A Study with a Special Reference to Assam	346 - 355
	- Nargis Choudhury, Former Faculty of Legal Studies, School of Law and Juridical Sciences Apex Professional University, Pasighat, Arunachal Pradesh	
26	The Doctrine of Pious Obligation and Its Relevance under the Hindu Law in the Present Time	356 - 363
	-Titikhya Barkataki, LL.M, 1st Semester, Gauhati University	
27	COVID-19 Pandemic: Justice Demands for Increasing Deterrence in India	364 - 370

- Jayanta Boruah, Research Scholar, North-Eastern Hill University, Former Assistant Professor of Law & Advocate & Sarthak Aryan, BALLB (3rd Year) National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam

SECTION C: LEGAL ESSAYS

- 28 **Traditional Ecological Knowledge and Biological Diversity Act, 2002: A Critical Analysis** 371 - 378
- Dr. Ravi Kanta Mishra, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, North-Eastern Hill University
- 29 **Trial by Media: A Hindrance in the Path of Justice and Fairness** 379 - 384
- Bidisha Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Kaustabh Moni Sarma, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 30 **Payment of Rent in Commercial Lease Contracts in Context of the COVID Crisis** 385 -391
- Clarissa D'Lima, Student Kirit P. Mehta School of Law, NMIMS Deemed-to-be University, Mumbai
- 31 **Adultery was Never a Crime: It is a Moral Wrong** 392 - 397
- Aadarsh Kumar Shrivastava, B.A.LL.B. 10th semester, Government New Law College Indore MP
- 32 **The Legal Protection for Consumers in Conducting E-Commerce Activities in India** 398 - 403
- Dikshita Nanda, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 33 **"Rarest of Rare Case"- Capital Punishment** 404 - 408
- Devika Warriar, Bharata Mata School of Legal Studies, Kerala
- 34 **Mob Lynching in India: A Threat to Mankind** 409 -413
- Nabanita Baruah, Student (BALLB 7th Sem), Department of Law, NERIM Law College
- 35 **Biomedical Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic in India** 414 - 418
- Farzin Naz, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 36 **Impact of Lockdown on Migrant Workers whether a Humanitarian or Human Rights Crisis?** 419 - 426
- Nikhil Moitra, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam
- 37 **Right to Privacy and Data Protection Law in India with a Brief Comparative Analysis with UK and USA** 427 - 433
- Bandana Saikia, Student, Symbiosis Law School Pune
- 38 **Rise of Pedophiles amidst Coronavirus Outbreak** 434 - 440
- Bulbul Kumari, Student, Dharmashastra National Law University, Jabalpur
- 39 **Arrest of Tax Evaders under the Central Goods and Service Tax Act 2017** 441 - 446
- Hunseng Tungkhang, Student, NERIM Law College

SECTION D: CASE COMMENTARY

- 40 **M/S. Nandhini Deluxe v. M/S. Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers Federation Ltd** 447 - 454
- Natesh Kumar, B.COM; LL.B.(HONS.), School of Law, SASTRA Deemed University
- 41 **The Interpretation of the Law of Limitation by the Indian Supreme Court during the COVID-19 Pandemic** 455 - 457
- Dr. Smarita Mohanty, Member, State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, Odisha
- 42 **Vineeta Sharma v. Rakesh Sharma** 458 - 460

	- <i>Namrata Chakrabarty, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	
43	Dunlop Pneumatic Tyre Co. Ltd. V. Selfridge & Co. Ltd.	461 - 463
	- <i>Chetna Priyam, BA LLB (Hons.), ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	
44	Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India	464 - 467
	- <i>Sristi Ray, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Kanika Chugh, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
45	Ashok Kumar Kalra v. Surendra Agnihotori (SLP No. 23599 of 2018)	468 - 470
	- <i>Monalisa Choudhury, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
46	Committee of Creditors Essar Steel India Limited Through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors.	471 - 475
	- <i>Rajat Gupta, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Vaishnavi Pandey, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
SECTION E: LEGISLATIVE ANALYSIS		
47	Relevance of Narcotics Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPs) Act, 1985	476 - 480
	- <i>Shivangi Pandey, LL.B.(CONST. LAW SPZ.) (5th Year), University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun</i>	
48	Analysis of the Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Bill, 2020	481 - 485
	- <i>Masia Baruah, Student BALLB 6th Semester, NERIM Law College</i>	
SECTION F: BOOK REVIEW		
49	Just Mercy: A Story of Justice and Redemption	486 - 487
	- <i>Aniket Jadhav, Student, Government Law College, Mumbai</i>	
50	Book Review on Judiciary, Judges and Administration of Justice	488 - 489
	- <i>Ishan Mishra, Student, ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	

SECTION (D) CASE COMMENTARY

**THE INTERPRETATION OF THE LAW OF LIMITATION BY THE INDIAN
SUPREME COURT DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC**

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INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of Corona Virus or COVID-19 worldwide, including India, has demanded immediate adoption of measures to ensure social distancing to prevent the spread of the virus. Following the World Health Organization (WHO) directive to combat the outbreak of Corona Virus (COVID-19) as a global pandemic, the government of India has taken several measures including lockdown and shut down.

In the wake of COVID-19 in the country, the Indian judiciary has taken ingenious steps to maintain a balance between public health concerns with access

to justice. Here the author discusses the extraordinary steps taken by the Apex court to alleviate the difficulties faced by litigants/lawyers in filing their petitions/applications/suits/appeals etc. within the period of limitation prescribed under General Law of Limitation or under Special Laws (both Central and/or State.

THE LAW OF LIMITATION

Limitation Act, 1963 defines 'Period of limitation' under Section 2(j), as a period of limitation prescribed for any suit, appeal, or application under the schedule to the Limitation Act, which covers a range of claims and their timelines.

The main objective of the statutory of the Limitation Act, 1963 is not to ruin or violate the rights of an aggrieved person but to serve the public most effectively as well as in a time-saving manner. It grants a specific time frame within which a person can file a suit in a court of law. In absence of such law specifying the period of limitation, it would lead to never-ending litigation.

The issue of limitation was first addressed by the High Court of Delhi in the office order dated 23.3.2020 wherein the following directions were passed:

“Lockdown/Suspension of work of Courts shall be treated as “closure” within the meaning of the Explanation appended to Section 4 of the Limitation Act, 1963 and other enabling provisions of the Act and other Statutes, as may be applied to court proceedings. Thus, the limitation for any court proceedings shall not run w.e.f. 23.3.2020 to 04.04.2020 subject to further orders.”

FACTUAL ASPECT OF THE CASE

The petition dated 23.3.2020 before the Hon’ble Supreme Court was taken up *suo motu* for hearing. Upon hearing the counsel the Court made the following observation:

“This court has taken Suo Motu cognizance of the situation arising out of the challenge faced by the country on account of Covid-19 virus and resultant

difficulties that may be faced by litigants across the country in filing their petitions/applications/suits/appeals/all other proceedings within the period of limitation prescribed under the general law of limitation or Special Laws (both Central and/or State).”

SUPREME COURT EXERCISING INHERENT POWERS IN PUBLIC INTEREST

In consideration of emerging difficulty and given the difficulties faced by lawyers and litigants across the country in filing petitions/applications/appeals etc. due to lockdown, the Supreme Court on the very same day “In re: Cognizance for Extension of Limitation, on 23rd March 2020 took up a *suo moto* petition for hearing while exercising its inherent powers under Article 142 read with Article 141 of the Indian Constitution, which allows it to pass a necessary decree or order for delivering complete justice in any cause or matter pending before the Court, took cognizance of challenges faced by lawyers, clients, and other court officials while filing legal documents (petitions/applications/suits/appeals, etc.) and adhering to other legal proceedings in Court which are barred by a limitation period under any General or Special Law (both Central and State) amid COVID-19”.

The three-judge bench comprising of Chief Justice S. A. Bobde, Justice L. Nageswar Rao, and Justice Surya Kant ordered that-

“a period of limitation in all such proceedings, irrespective of the limitation prescribed under the General Law or Special Laws whether condonable or not shall stand extended w.e.f 15th March 2020 till further order/s to be passed by the Court in present proceedings. We are exercising this power under Article 142 read with Article 141 of the Constitution of India and declare that this order is a binding order within the meaning of Article 141 on all Courts/Tribunals and authorities.”

This welcoming move of the Hon’ble Supreme Court has eased the lawyers/litigants as an immediate relief.

In terms of the order of the Hon’ble Supreme Court, National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission was pleased to follow the said order from 15.3.2020 till further orders.

CONCLUSION

Indian judicial bodies have taken immediate and necessary steps during the pandemic. This has opened a new avenue in the upcoming difficulty faced by lawyers/litigants. The Judiciary has a brilliant opportunity to foresee a judicial system that could function uninterrupted at all levels during any emergency. Therefore, there is an immediate need to re-organize the entire judicial system to make it accountable to the needs of a democratic progressive society.